

Temporal Dynamics of Problematic Internet Use in Undergraduates: Disentangling Academic and Leisure-Related Usage Patterns During Pre-Pandemic and Pandemic Periods

Assist. Prof. Dr. Yüksel ÇIRAK
Malatya İnönü University-Türkiye
ORCID: 0000-0001-8325-9680
yukse.cirak@inonu.edu.tr

Abstract

Problematic Internet Use (PIU) has become a critical issue in the digital age, with the COVID-19 pandemic dramatically reshaping how undergraduate students engage with online technologies for both education and entertainment. This study aims to explore the temporal dynamics of PIU by disentangling the specific impacts of academic and leisure-related usage patterns during pre-pandemic and pandemic periods. Utilizing a correlational research design, data were collected from a convenience sample of 850 undergraduate students (546 females, 304 males) attending public universities. The study compared data across two distinct timeframes: the pre-pandemic period (2018-2019) and the pandemic period (2020-2021). Participants completed the Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale-2 (GPIUS2) and reported average daily durations for academic and leisure internet activities. A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictors of PIU. The model significantly explained 8% of the total variance in problematic use. The findings demonstrated distinct trajectories for different types of online engagement: the duration of leisure-related internet use was positively associated with PIU, whereas the duration of academic internet use showed a negative association. Furthermore, the study identified significant temporal and demographic predictors, with the pandemic period associated with higher levels of PIU compared to the pre-pandemic era. Regarding gender, male students exhibited lower levels of PIU compared to their female counterparts. These results suggest that the context of internet use—whether goal-oriented or recreational—plays a crucial role in the development of problematic behaviors. The findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions that address specific usage patterns.

Keywords: University, Undergraduates, Pandemic, Internet use

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INTRODUCTION

Problematic internet use (PIU) has emerged as a growing concern in the digital age, with individuals increasingly relying on the internet for various aspects of their daily lives, such as education, work, communication, and leisure (Balhara et al., 2018; Kuss et al., 2014). Characterized by excessive or uncontrolled use of the internet (Caplan, 2010), PIU can result in negative outcomes, such as impaired academic performance (Skues et al., 2016; Yavuz & Toprakçı, 2021) sleep disturbances (Lam, 2014), and mental health issues (Takahashi et al., 2018;), including anxiety (Ramón-Arbués et al., 2021), depression (Xie et al., 2021), and social isolation (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011; Stavropoulos et al., 2019; Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023). Research has shown that students, in particular, are vulnerable to PIU due to their extensive use of the internet for leisure-related purposes (Kuss et al., 2014; Lam, 2014; Vadher et al., 2019). On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered daily routines and lifestyles, leading to increased reliance on the internet for remote work, education, and social interaction (Cellini et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2020; Toprakçı, Hepsöğütlü & Toprakçı, 2021; Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023). Before the pandemic, PIU was already a growing concern (Oka et al., 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has intensified concerns surrounding it, as the sudden transition to remote learning and the decline in face-to-face interactions have led to increased internet usage among students, heightening the risk of PIU (Odriozola-González et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020). With the internet now playing an integral role in contemporary education and social life, it is vital to comprehend the factors that contribute to PIU among students, as well as how these factors may evolve, particularly during uncertain times such as COVID-19 pandemic. This understanding is crucial for the development of effective interventions and the promotion of healthy internet habits (Kuss et al., 2014; Ortuño-Sierra et al., 2022). Moreover, as the pandemic persists in shaping the digital landscape (Zhang & Wang, 2022; Xie et al., 2021), it becomes increasingly imperative to investigate the impact of both academic and leisure-related internet use on PIU among students, with the aim of supporting their well-being and fostering responsible internet usage patterns (Balhara et al., 2021; Király et al., 2020).

Over the past few decades, internet use durations have increased significantly due to the rapid expansion of internet access, greater availability of online content, and the development of various online platforms and services (Jovic et al., 2020; Kemp, 2022). In the early days of the internet, usage was often limited to a few hours per week, primarily for activities such as email and basic web browsing (Nie, 2001). However, the rise of social media platforms, online gaming, streaming services, and other forms of digital entertainment has contributed to a substantial growth in the time spent online by users of all ages (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011; Jackson et al., 2021; Lenhart, 2015). The COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated this trend, with many individuals increasing their internet use durations for work, education, communication, and leisure purposes due to lockdown measures and social distancing requirements (Fernandes et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020). Research indicates that individuals currently spend numerous hours online each day, with certain reports proposing that the average daily internet usage may extend to approximately 7 hours for typical users (Kemp, 2022). Several studies have demonstrated that internet use duration plays a significant role in the development of PIU behavior (Laconi et al., 2015; Caner-Yıldırım & Yıldırım, 2022). Prolonged periods of internet use, particularly for non-academic or leisure-related purposes, have been associated with an increased risk of PIU, as extended online activity can disrupt daily routines, negatively impact academic performance, and hinder social life (Caplan, 2010; Kuss & Griffiths, 2011; Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023). Excessive internet use duration may contribute to the development of compulsive online habits, which, in turn, can lead to psychological distress, reduced well-being, and other adverse outcomes (Gao et al., 2020; Lebni et al., 2020). Understanding the relationship between internet use duration and PIU is crucial for identifying risk factors and developing effective interventions to mitigate the negative consequences of excessive internet use (Dhir, Chen & Nieminen, 2015; Van den Eijnden, Lemmens & Valkenburg, 2016).

1. Academic and Problematic Internet Use During Pre-Pandemic and Pandemic Periods

The role of the internet in modern education has become increasingly significant in recent years, as digital technologies have transformed the way students access information, engage with learning materials, and interact with their peers and instructors (Bates, 2015; Mehrvarz et al., 2021; Stosic et al., 2020). With the widespread availability of internet-enabled devices and the growing reliance on online resources, the internet has fundamentally altered educational practices, both inside and outside the classroom (Collins & Halverson, 2018; Mehrvarz et al., 2021). Up-to-date studies on the association between academic internet use duration and PIU suggest that the relationship is complex and can be influenced by various factors, such as individual traits, self-regulation, and academic stress (Chen & Nath, 2016; Laconi et al., 2015). In a study by Balhara et al. (2018), it was found that academic internet use duration was positively correlated with fewer problems regarding PIU. On the other hand, with the COVID-19 pandemic, the shift to remote learning has led to a surge in academic internet use and a decrease in face-to-face interactions (Fernandes et al., 2020). The unprecedented circumstances brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic have presented students, educators, and policymakers with novel challenges in striking a balance between academic internet use and the potential risks of PIU. Consequently, it is essential to compare the relationships between academic internet use and PIU across both pandemic and non-pandemic contexts. Such comparisons enable the identification of potential differences in these dynamics, thereby informing the development of effective strategies to support students across a range of learning environments.

1.1. Leisure-Related and Problematic Internet Use During Pre-Pandemic and Pandemic Periods

Leisure-related internet use encompasses a wide variety of online activities, which people engage in for entertainment, relaxation, and social connection. Common leisure-related internet activities include social media, online gaming, and video streaming. Social media platforms, such as Twitter, Instagram, TikTok and Facebook, allow users to share content, interact with others, and stay informed about current events (Kemp, 2022; Perrin & Anderson, 2019). While leisure-related internet use can offer numerous benefits, such as relaxation, social connection, and stress relief, it is important to recognize that it may also have negative impacts on mental health and well-being. Excessive use of social media has been linked to increased feelings of loneliness, anxiety, and depression (Primack et al., 2017; Vannucci et al., 2017). Besides, compulsive online gaming has been associated with social isolation, sleep problems, and reduced academic performance (Kuss & Griffiths, 2012). Binge-watching video streaming content can also contribute to sedentary behavior, sleep disruption, and negative mood states (Exelmans & Van den Bulck, 2017; Flayelle et al., 2019) emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to leisure-related internet use. The association between leisure-related internet use and PIU has been studied both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Prior to the pandemic, numerous studies found significant associations between increased leisure-related internet use, including excessive social media use, online gaming, and video streaming, and PIU (Kuss & Griffiths, 2012; Primack et al., 2017). During the pandemic, the relationship between leisure-related internet use and PIU has become even more significant, as individuals spend more time indoors due to lockdown measures, social distancing requirements, and remote work or education (Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023; Odriozola-González et al., 2020). Studies conducted during the pandemic suggest that the increased reliance on leisure-related internet activities has further exacerbated PIU (Gao et al., 2020; Putri et al., 2022). In particular, the pandemic has led to an increase in social media consumption, online gaming, and binge-watching of streaming content, which in turn may heighten the risk of PIU and associated negative mental health outcomes (Sun et al., 2020). It is important to note that the pandemic has intensified existing trends and relationships, rather than creating entirely new dynamics between leisure-related internet use and PIU. This emphasizes the need for continued research to understand the evolving nature of these relationships,

as well as the development of adaptive strategies for promoting healthy internet habits in the context of the ongoing pandemic and beyond (Gao et al., 2020; Putri et al., 2022).

2. Problematic Internet Use During Pre-Pandemic and Pandemic Periods

Comparing PIU in pre-pandemic and pandemic periods highlights the role external factors, like a global crisis, play in worsening existing internet use concerns. Although the core risk factors for PIU stay constant, the pandemic has amplified some of these factors, leading to increased vulnerability to PIU (Sun et al., 2020). One major difference between pre-pandemic and pandemic periods is the overall growth in internet usage. Due to pandemic-related restrictions, people rely more on the internet for work, education, and socialization (Cellini et al., 2020; Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023). This increased exposure to PIU risk factors, such as excessive engagement in certain online activities and disrupted routines, has resulted in a higher prevalence of PIU in the pandemic period (Ammar et al., 2020). Another key difference between the two periods is the effect of pandemic-related stress, anxiety, and social isolation on PIU. These factors make individuals more prone to PIU by promoting unhealthy coping strategies like excessive internet use as an escape from negative emotions and feelings of isolation (King et al., 2020; Király et al., 2020). Despite these differences, many risk factors for PIU identified pre-pandemic remain relevant during the pandemic. In essence, the pandemic has simply intensified these factors' impact, making it vital to address PIU and encourage healthy internet habits during these challenging times.

3. Problematic Internet Use and Gender during Pre-Pandemic and Pandemic Periods

Gender differences in PIU have been a topic of interest in the literature. Prior to the pandemic, studies examining gender differences in PIU reported mixed findings. Some studies found that males were more prone to PIU, particularly in relation to online gaming, while females were more likely to exhibit excessive social media use (Haagsma et al., 2012; Kuss et al., 2014). Other studies found no significant gender differences in PIU (Caner-Yıldırım & Yıldırım, 2022; Vigna-Taglianti et al., 2017). These results suggest that the relationship between gender and PIU may be complex and influenced by factors such as individual personality traits, cultural context, and the type of online activities engaged in.

The internet related shift in internet use patterns during Covid-19 pandemic period may have affected the relationship between gender and PIU. For instance, the sudden increase in remote learning and online communication may have amplified stress, anxiety, and social isolation, potentially affecting males and females differently in terms of PIU risk (Aristovnik et al., 2020; Elmer et al., 2020). Additionally, the surge in leisure-related internet use during the pandemic may have disproportionately impacted males and females depending on their preferred online activities, such as gaming or social media use (Ammar et al., 2020; Király et al., 2020).

In light of the growing concern surrounding PIU, particularly among students, and the unprecedented changes in internet use patterns during the COVID-19 pandemic, understanding the factors contributing to PIU and how they evolve over time is of utmost importance. This knowledge also is essential for developing effective interventions and promoting healthy internet habits, especially considering the significant role the internet plays in modern education and social life. In the current study, the guiding research question seeks to explore the potential differences in PIU between students with varying academic and leisure-related internet use durations and examine how these differences may change over time.

To address this question, it is crucial to first investigate the complex relationships between PIU, academic internet use, and leisure-related internet use in both pre-pandemic and pandemic contexts. This includes examining the potential gender differences in PIU and how the pandemic may have impacted these differences. By exploring these relationships, researchers can better understand the underlying factors that contribute to PIU among students and gain insight into the temporal dynamics of PIU in response to external influences, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Ultimately, this

research will inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at supporting students' well-being and fostering healthy internet usage patterns in both academic and leisure contexts.

The guiding research question is: What are the differences in the temporal dynamics of PIU among undergraduates between academic and leisure-related usage patterns during pre-pandemic and pandemic periods?

METHOD

Given the purpose of this study, which is to explore the differences in the temporal dynamics of PIU among undergraduates between academic and leisure-related usage patterns during pre-pandemic and pandemic periods, a correlational research approach was employed. Fraenkel et al. (2012) assert that there are two primary reasons for conducting correlational studies: first, to explain human behaviors, and second, to predict potential outcomes. This study focuses on the latter reason, aiming to predict the possible impacts of internet usage patterns on PIU among undergraduates during different time periods.

1. Participants and Procedures

Paper and online surveys were employed to gather data. Ethical committee approval and informed consent were obtained from the participants. The study group comprised students from two accessible public universities for both the pre-pandemic and during-pandemic data collection procedures. Creswell (2012) defines convenience (nonprobability) sampling as the selection of participants based on their availability and representation of the study's aim. As the data were collected from readily available participants, the sampling method utilized in this study is convenience sampling. The sample included a total of 850 students (546 female and 304 male) from the 2018-2019 (pre-pandemic period) and 2020-2021 (during pandemic period) academic years. Table 1 displays the gender distribution of participants during pre-pandemic and pandemic periods.

Table 1 Gender distribution of participants during pre-pandemic (n= 479) and pandemic periods (n= 371)

Gender	Pre-Pandemic		Pandemic		Total
	f	%	f	%	f
Female	291	53.3	255	46.7	546
Male	188	61.8	116	38.2	304
Total	479	56.4	371	43.6	850

2. Data Collection Procedures and Instruments

Both ethical committee approval (Ref. No: E.15006-Inönü University) and informed consent of participants was gathered before the data collection procedures. For the pre-pandemic study, data collection was conducted using both online and paper-based questionnaires. In each survey format, the study's details were thoroughly explained, and participant consent was obtained through statements explicitly requesting their agreement. In the pandemic period data collection procedure, initially, two faculty members from the Department of Guidance and Psychological Counseling posted an online survey on their course pages for one month. Next, the pages informed students that they could earn extra credit for the respective course by volunteering to participate in the survey, and interested volunteers could access the survey via a provided link. Subsequently, the online survey's opening page furnished detailed information about the research and stated that student identification numbers were required for extra credit. However, it was emphasized that this data would only be used for this specific purpose and would not lead to any other alterations in their courses. Lastly, it was conveyed that students who wished to volunteer for the study should select the statement "I would like to participate in the study," and informed consent was obtained in this manner.

The data collection instruments were designed to gather information on participants' gender, PIU, academic internet use duration, and leisure-related internet use duration. Besides demographic information, following instruments were employed:

Translated version of the Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale-2 (GPIUS2): It was employed to assess problematic internet use among the participants. The scale was adapted and validated for use in the population by Caner-Yıldırım and Yıldırım (2022). This 14-item instrument comprises three factors: deficient self-regulation (of internet use), preference for online social interaction, and (internet use for) mood regulation. The items are rated on an 8-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 8 (strongly agree). The overall reliability of this version of GPIUS2 was found to be Cronbach's $\alpha = .88$.

Academic Internet Use Duration: A single-item self-report measure was used to assess the average daily duration of academic internet use. Participants were asked to report the approximate number of hours they spent on the internet for academic purposes (e.g., online learning, research, communication with instructors) per day.

Leisure-Related Internet Use Duration: A single-item self-report measure was used to assess the average daily duration of leisure-related internet use. Participants were asked to report the approximate number of hours they spent on the internet for leisure purposes (e.g., social media, gaming, video streaming) per day.

3. Data Analysis

To address the research question, we conducted a multiple linear regression analysis to explore the temporal dynamics of PIU among undergraduates, taking into account academic and leisure-related usage patterns during both pre-pandemic and pandemic periods. This analytical approach allowed us to examine the relationships between the academic internet use duration, and leisure-related internet use duration, period, and gender (independent variables) and the PIU (dependent variable). The analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Before conducting the multiple linear regression analysis, gender variable was coded as female = 1, male = 2 and the period was coded as pre-pandemic = 1, pandemic = 2. The assumptions we assessed included linearity, independence of errors, homoscedasticity, multicollinearity, and normality of residuals (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). A scatterplot of the relationship between each independent variable and PIU was visually inspected to confirm that the relationships were linear. Additionally, partial regression plots were examined to ensure that the linearity assumption held when controlling for other variables. To test for independence of errors, we calculated the Durbin-Watson statistic, which revealed no significant autocorrelation among the residuals. A plot of standardized residuals against predicted values was inspected, revealing a random distribution of residuals across the range of predicted values, thus indicating homoscedasticity. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were computed for each independent variable, and all VIF values were found to be well below the threshold of 10, indicating that multicollinearity was not a concern in the analysis. The distribution of residuals was assessed through a visual inspection of the histogram and Q-Q plot, as well as by conducting the Shapiro-Wilk test. The results confirmed that the residuals were normally distributed. Given that all the assumptions of multiple linear regression were satisfied, we proceeded with the analysis to address the research question in our study.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the results of the multiple linear regression analysis conducted to investigate the temporal dynamics of PIU among undergraduates, considering the differences between academic and leisure-related usage patterns during the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods.

1. Descriptive Statistics

Before discussing the results of the regression analysis, we report the descriptive statistics for the variables included in the study. Table 2 displays the mean and standard deviation for PIU, academic internet use duration (in hours), and leisure-related internet use duration (in hours)

separately for the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods.

Table 2 Mean and standard deviation for PIU, academic internet use duration, leisure-related internet use duration for pre-pandemic and pandemic periods

	Pre-pandemic Period		Pandemic Period	
	M	SD	M	SD
Problematic internet use (PIU)	3.21	1.27	3.51	1.31
Academic internet use duration (in hours)	1.75	1.19	3.94	1.96
Leisure-related internet use duration (in hours)	4.49	3.29	5.11	2.36

2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to explore the relationships between PIU and the independent variables of academic internet use duration, leisure-related internet use duration, period (pre-pandemic or pandemic), and gender. Table 3 presents the results of the regression analysis, including the unstandardized coefficients (B), standard error of the unstandardized regression coefficient (SE B), standardized coefficients (Beta), t-values, and significance levels (p-values) for each predictor variable.

Table 3 Summary of multiple regression analysis for variables predicting problematic internet use (N=850)

Variable	B	SE B	β	t	sr ²	R ²	ΔF
Model						.08	19.386**
Academic internet use duration (in hours)	-.073	.028	-.108	-2.654**	-.09		
Leisure-related internet use duration (in hours)	.114	.015	.257	7.703**	.26		
Period (pre-pandemic or pandemic)	.378	.105	.145	3.616**	.12		
Gender	-.217	.090	-.080	-2.395*	-.08		

**p<.001, *p<.01.

The overall model was significant, with an R² value of .08, which indicates that 8% of the variance in PIU can be explained by the independent variables (academic internet use duration, leisure-related internet use duration, period, and gender). The change in F statistic (ΔF) was 19.386, which is significant at p < .001, suggesting that the model is a good fit for the data. Academic internet use duration (in hours): The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) is -.073, and it is significant at p < .001. This means that for each additional hour of academic internet use, PIU is predicted to decrease by .073 units, holding all other variables constant. The standardized regression coefficient (β) is -.108, indicating that a one standard deviation increase in academic internet use duration is associated with a .108 standard deviation decrease in PIU. Leisure-related internet use duration (in hours): The B value is .114, and it is significant at p < .001. This means that for each additional hour of leisure-related internet use, PIU is predicted to increase by .114 units, holding all other variables constant. The β value is .257, indicating that a one standard deviation increase in leisure-related internet use duration is associated with a .257 standard deviation increase in PIU. Period (pre-pandemic or pandemic): The B value is .378, and it is significant at p < .001. Since the period was coded as pre-pandemic = 1 and pandemic = 2, this means that PIU is predicted to be .378 units higher during the pandemic than before the pandemic, holding all other variables constant. The β value is .145, indicating that being in the pandemic period is associated with a .145 standard deviation increase in PIU compared to the pre-pandemic period. Gender: The B value is -.217, and it is significant at p < .01. Since gender was coded as female = 1 and male = 2, this means that PIU is predicted to be .217 units lower for males compared to females, holding all other variables constant. The β value is -.080, indicating that being male is associated with a .080 standard deviation decrease in PIU compared to being female.

In summary, the results suggest that leisure-related internet use duration and the pandemic period are positively associated with PIU, while academic internet use duration and being male are

negatively associated with PIU.

The present study aimed to examine the relationships between PIU and academic internet use duration, leisure-related internet use duration, the period (pre-pandemic or pandemic), and gender. The multiple linear regression analysis revealed that 8% of the variance in PIU could be explained by these independent variables. Our findings contribute to the growing body of literature on the factors associated with PIU in the digital age, particularly in the COVID-19 pandemic context, which has substantially impacted daily routines, lifestyles, and internet usage patterns.

Our findings showed a negative relationship between academic internet use duration and PIU, suggesting that as the number of hours spent on academic internet use increases, PIU tends to decrease. This result aligns with previous research indicating that increased academic internet use means a decrease in PIU (Caner-Yıldırım & Yıldırım, 2022; Romero-Rodríguez et al., 2022). It is possible that the nature of academic internet use, which often involves goal-directed tasks and structured activities, could be less likely to lead to compulsive or maladaptive internet behaviors.

We found a positive relationship between leisure-related internet use duration and PIU. This finding is consistent with prior research demonstrating that excessive leisure-related internet use, such as gaming, social networking, communication or online shopping, can be a risk factor for developing PIU (Caplan, 2010; Kuss et al., 2014; Toprakçı, 2007). Leisure-related internet use often entails more unstructured and engaging activities, which could increase the likelihood of excessive use and the development of problematic behaviors. This result highlights the importance of understanding the role of leisure-related internet use in the development of PIU and the need for targeted interventions and prevention strategies to promote healthy online habits.

The period variable, which differentiated between pre-pandemic and pandemic timeframes, showed a positive association with PIU. Our results indicate that PIU was higher during the pandemic compared to the pre-pandemic period. This finding is in line with recent studies highlighting the increased prevalence of PIU during the COVID-19 pandemic due to factors such as increased stress, social isolation, and a greater reliance on digital technology for work, education, and entertainment (Sun et al., 2020; Ünlü-Sakıcı & Toprakçı, 2024; Yıldırım & Caner-Yıldırım, 2023). Our results emphasize the need for ongoing research and interventions to support students' well-being and foster healthy internet usage patterns during challenging times such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Regarding gender, our analysis revealed that males had lower levels of PIU compared to females. This finding contrasts with some previous research suggesting that males are more prone to PIU (Haagsma et al., 2012; Toprakçı, 2007). Further research is needed to explore the underlying factors contributing to gender differences in PIU, taking into account the potential confounding and suppressor effects of other variables.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, this study elucidates the distinct temporal dynamics of Problematic Internet Use (PIU) among undergraduates, revealing that the purpose of online engagement is a critical determinant of its impact. Specifically, while academic internet use appears to serve as a protective factor associated with lower PIU—likely due to its structured and goal-directed nature—leisure-related use emerges as a significant predictor of problematic behavior. The findings also underscore the exacerbating role of external crises, as PIU levels were notably higher during the pandemic compared to the pre-pandemic period, highlighting the need for supportive interventions during such challenging times. Furthermore, the observation that males exhibited lower PIU levels than females challenges some previous literature and suggests a need to further investigate the gender-specific mechanisms underlying these behaviors. Ultimately, these results imply that fostering healthy internet habits requires a nuanced approach that distinguishes between beneficial academic engagement and

potentially harmful unstructured leisure activities.

Despite the valuable insights provided by this study, there are several limitations that should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings. First, this sample may not be representative of the broader population, limiting the generalizability of the findings. The study focused on a specific group of students, which might not reflect the experiences of other demographic groups or individuals from different cultural backgrounds. Future studies could explore these relationships in more diverse samples, including individuals from various age groups, educational levels, and cultural contexts, to better understand the factors contributing to PIU across different populations. Second, self-report measures were used to assess the variables in this study, which could introduce biases due to social desirability or inaccurate recall. Future research may benefit from incorporating alternative assessment methods, such as behavioral observations, experience sampling, or objective measures of internet use, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors associated with PIU. Finally, the present study focused on a limited set of independent variables, and other factors that may contribute to PIU were not examined. Future research could explore additional variables, such as personality traits, coping strategies, social support, and mental health, to gain a more complete understanding of the determinants of PIU. Additionally, investigating the potential moderating or mediating effects of these factors on the relationships between internet use duration, period, gender, and PIU could provide valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms and help inform the development of targeted interventions to address PIU.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the temporal dynamics of PIU among undergraduates during pre-pandemic and pandemic periods. Findings suggest that leisure-related internet use and the pandemic period are positively associated with PIU, while academic internet use and being male are negatively associated with PIU. These results highlight the importance of considering the context and purpose of internet use when examining PIU among undergraduates. Future research should continue to explore the factors contributing to PIU to inform targeted prevention and intervention strategies that promote healthy internet use behaviors among young adults.

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Lisans Öğrencilerinde Problemlı İnternet Kullanımının Zamansal Dinamikleri: Pandemi Öncesi ve Pandemi Dönemlerinde Akademik ve Boş Zaman Kullanım Örüntülerinin Ayrıştırılması

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Yüksel ÇIRAK
Malatya İnönü Üniversitesi-Türkiye
ORCID: 0000-0001-8325-9680
yukse.cirak@inonu.edu.tr

Özet

Problemlı İnternet Kullanımı (PİK), dijital çağda kritik bir sorun haline gelmiştir. COVID-19 salgını, lisans öğrencilerinin hem eğitim hem de eğlence amaçlı çevrimiçi teknolojileri kullanma biçimlerini önemli ölçüde değiştirmiştir. Bu çalışma, salgın öncesi ve salgın dönemlerinde akademik ve eğlence amaçlı kullanım modellerinin spesifik etkilerini ayırarak PIU'nun zamansal dinamiklerini araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Korelasyonel bir araştırma tasarımı kullanılarak, devlet üniversitelerine devam eden 850 lisans öğrencisinden (546 kadın, 304 erkek) oluşan bir kolaylık örnekleminde veriler toplanmıştır. Çalışma, iki farklı zaman dilimindeki verileri karşılaştırmıştır: pandemi öncesi dönem (2018-2019) ve pandemi dönemi (2020-2021). Katılımcılar, Genelleştirilmiş Problemlı İnternet Kullanımı Ölçeği-2'yi (GPIUS2) doldurmuş ve akademik ve eğlence amaçlı internet faaliyetleri için ortalama günlük süreleri bildirmiştir. PIU'nun belirleyicilerini belirlemek için çoklu doğrusal regresyon analizi yapılmıştır. Model, problemlı kullarımdaki toplam varyansın %8'ini önemli ölçüde açıklamıştır. Bulgular, farklı türdeki çevrimiçi etkileşimler için farklı eğilimler ortaya koydu: eğlence amaçlı internet kullanım süresi PİK ile pozitif bir ilişki gösterirken, akademik amaçlı internet kullanım süresi negatif bir ilişki gösterdi. Ayrıca, çalışma önemli zamansal ve demografik belirleyiciler tespit etti; pandemi dönemi, pandemi öncesi döneme kıyasla daha yüksek PIU düzeyleriyle ilişkiliydi. Cinsiyet açısından, erkek öğrenciler kadın öğrencilere kıyasla daha düşük PİK düzeyleri sergiledi. Bu sonuçlar, internet kullanımının bağlamının (hedef odaklı veya eğlence amaçlı) problemlı davranışların gelişmesinde önemli bir rol oynadığını göstermektedir. Sonuçlar özellikle pandemi gibi zorlu dönemlerde öğrencilerin iyi oluşunu desteklemek için kullanım türüne özgü müdahalelerin geliştirilmesi gerektiğini vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Üniversite, Lisans Öğrencileri, Pandemi, İnternet kullanımı

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Geniştirilmiş Özet

Problem: Dijital çağda internet, eğitimden sosyal etkileşime kadar günlük yaşamın ayrılmaz bir parçası haline gelmiştir. Ancak bu yoğun kullanım, bireylerin işlevselliğini bozan Problemlerli İnternet Kullanımı (PİK) riskini de beraberinde getirmektedir. Özellikle üniversite öğrencileri, boş zamanlarını değerlendirmek amacıyla yoğun internet kullanımını sergiledikleri için PİK açısından risk grubu olarak değerlendirilmektedir. COVID-19 pandemisi ise zorunlu izolasyon, uzaktan eğitim ve sosyal kısıtlamalar nedeniyle öğrencilerin internet kullanım alışkanlıklarında köklü değişikliklere yol açmıştır. Pandemi öncesinde de var olan endişeler, pandemi sürecinde artan ekran süreleriyle daha karmaşık bir hal almıştır.

Literatürde internet kullanım süresinin PİK üzerindeki etkisi sıklıkla incelenmiş olsa da, kullanımın "amacı" (akademik veya boş zaman) ve "dönemi" (pandemi öncesi ve sırası) arasındaki etkileşimlerin netleştirilmesine ihtiyaç vardır. Bazı çalışmalar akademik kullanımın koruyucu olabileceğini öne sürerken, boş zaman kullanımının riski artırdığı belirtilmektedir. Bu araştırmanın temel amacı, lisans öğrencilerinde PİK'in zamansal dinamiklerini; akademik ve boş zamanla ilgili internet kullanım sürelerinin etkilerini ayırıştırarak, pandemi öncesi ve pandemi dönemleri bağlamında incelemektir. Böylece, kriz dönemlerinde öğrencilerin dijital refahını destekleyecek faktörlerin belirlenmesi hedeflenmektedir.

Yöntem: Bu çalışmada, değişkenler arasındaki ilişkileri var olduğu şekliyle incelemeyi amaçlayan ilişkisel tarama modeli (correlational research design) kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu, Türkiye'deki iki farklı kamu üniversitesinde öğrenim gören toplam 850 lisans öğrencisi oluşturmaktadır. Katılımcıların 546'sı (%64,2) kadın, 304'ü (%35,8) erkektir. Veri toplama süreci iki ayrı zaman diliminde gerçekleştirilmiştir: Pandemi öncesi veriler 2018-2019 akademik yılında, pandemi dönemi verileri ise 2020-2021 akademik yılında toplanmıştır. Örneklem yöntemi olarak uygun örneklem (convenience sampling) tercih edilmiştir.

Veri toplama aracı olarak, katılımcıların problemlerli internet kullanım düzeylerini belirlemek amacıyla Genelleştirilmiş Problemlerli İnternet Kullanımı Ölçeği-2 (GPIUS2) kullanılmıştır. Ölçeğin Türkçe uyarlaması kullanılmış olup, bu çalışmadaki iç tutarlılık katsayısı (Cronbach alfa) .88 olarak hesaplanmıştır. Ayrıca, öğrencilerin günlük ortalama "Akademik İnternet Kullanım Süresi" ve "Boş Zamanla İlgili İnternet Kullanım Süresi"ni belirlemek için tek maddelik öz bildirim soruları kullanılmıştır. Verilerin analizinde, PİK üzerindeki yordayıcı etkileri belirlemek amacıyla cinsiyet, dönem, akademik kullanım süresi ve boş zaman kullanım süresi değişkenlerinin dahil edildiği çoklu doğrusal regresyon analizi uygulanmıştır.

Sonuçlar: Araştırma verileri üzerinde gerçekleştirilen çoklu doğrusal regresyon analizi sonucunda, kurulan modelin istatistiksel olarak anlamlı olduğu ve Problemlerli İnternet Kullanımındaki varyansın %8'ini açıkladığı görülmüştür ($R^2 = .08$, $p < .001$). Bağımsız değişkenlerin PİK üzerindeki etkileri incelendiğinde çarpıcı sonuçlara ulaşılmıştır. "Boş zamanla ilgili internet kullanım süresi" ile PİK arasında pozitif yönde ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir ilişki saptanmıştır ($\beta = .257$); yani eğlence amaçlı kullanım süresi arttıkça problemlerli kullanım düzeyi artmaktadır. Buna karşılık, "Akademik internet kullanım süresi" ile PİK arasında negatif yönde anlamlı bir ilişki bulunmuştur ($\beta = -.108$). Bu bulgu, akademik amaçlı çevrimiçi geçirilen sürenin artmasının, problemlerli kullanım riskini azaltıcı bir faktör olabileceğini göstermektedir.

Dönem değişkeni açısından bakıldığında, pandemi döneminde olmanın PİK puanlarını pozitif yönde yordadığı görülmüştür; pandemi sürecindeki öğrencilerin PİK düzeyleri, pandemi öncesi döneme göre anlamlı derecede daha yüksektir. Cinsiyet değişkeni incelendiğinde ise, erkek öğrencilerin PİK düzeylerinin kadın öğrencilere kıyasla anlamlı derecede daha düşük olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak çalışma, internet kullanımının bağlamının (yapılandırılmış akademik görevler

vs. yapılandırılmamış boş zaman aktiviteleri) problemleri davranışların gelişiminde belirleyici olduğunu ortaya koymuştur.

Öneriler: Elde edilen bulgular ışığında, PİK ile mücadelede internet kullanımının sadece süresine değil, niteliğine ve amacına odaklanması gerektiği görülmektedir. Uygulayıcılar ve psikolojik danışmanlar, öğrencilere yönelik geliştirecekleri müdahale programlarında, internetin akademik ve hedef odaklı kullanımını teşvik ederken; sosyal medya, oyun veya video izleme gibi yapılandırılmamış boş zaman etkinliklerinde öz düzenleme becerilerini artırmaya odaklanmalıdır. Özellikle pandemi gibi kriz dönemlerinde artan stres ve izolasyonun PİK riskini artırdığı göz önüne alınarak, bu tür dönemlerde öğrencilere yönelik psikososyal destek hizmetleri artırılmalıdır.

Araştırmada erkeklerin PİK düzeylerinin daha düşük çıkması, bazı literatür bulgularıyla farklılık gösterdiğinden, gelecekteki çalışmalarda cinsiyetin PİK üzerindeki etkisinin altında yatan kültürel ve bireysel mekanizmaların derinlemesine incelenmesi önerilir. Ayrıca, bu çalışmanın kesitsel doğası bir sınırlılık olduğundan, gelecekteki araştırmaların boylamsal desenler kullanarak akademik ve boş zaman kullanımının PİK üzerindeki uzun vadeli etkilerini takip etmesi, alanyazına önemli katkılar sağlayacaktır.